

Synthesis, Spectral and Anticarboxylesterase Properties of 3-Substituted-1,5-dihydro-7,8-dimethyl-2,4,3-benzodioxaphosphepin-3-oxides

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In continuation of our studies on the synthesis of new biologically active organophosphorus heterocyclic compounds, we undertook the preparation of benzodioxaphosphepin-3-oxides. The title compounds (1a—m) were prepared by the condensation of phosphorodichloridates with 4,5-dimethyl-1,2-benzenedimethanol in dry tetrahydrofuran in the presence of triethylamine. On the other hand, the preparation of 3-substituted-1,5-dihydro-7,8-dimethyl-2,4,3-benzodioxaphosphepin-3-oxides (2a—e) were achieved in two steps, through the intermediate monochloride, 3-chloro-1,5-dihydro-7,8-dimethyl-2,4,3-benzodioxaphosphepin-3-oxides (1; R = Cl), the preparation of which was accomplished by the treatment of phosphorusoxychloride with 4,5-dimethyl-1,2-dihydroxymethyl in the presence of triethylamine. The monochloride (1; R = Cl) thus obtained was treated *in situ* with respective nucleophiles to get 2a—e.

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| 1a; R = C ₆ H ₅ | 1h; R = 2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ O |
| 1b; R = C ₆ H ₄ O | 1i; R = 2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ O |
| 1c; R = 2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ O | 1j; R = 3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ O |
| 1d; R = 4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ O | 1k; R = 3,5-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ O |
| 1e; R = 2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ O | 1l; R = 4-Cl-3-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ O |
| 1f; R = 3-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ O | 1m; R = 2,4-Cl ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ O |
| 1g; R = 4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ O | |
| 2a; R = Piperazine | 2d; R = 4-Chlorothiophenol |
| 2b; R = Dicyclohexylamine | 2e; R = <i>N</i> -Methylaniline |
| 2c; R = 8-Hydroxyquinoline | |

IR spectra of 1a—m and 2a—e showed medium to strong bands¹ in the regions 1 320—1 300, 1 320—1 260 (P=O), 1 190—1 130, 1 240—1 160 (P—O—C aryl), 1 190—1 130 and 1 200—1 100 (P—O—C aliphatic). In ¹H nmr spectra, methylene protons displaying six-line signal is contrary to the expected eight-line AB part of ABX pattern X being phosphorus². The methylene proton of 2a—e appeared as multiplets due to coupling between phosphorus and methylene protons. The ¹³C nmr spectra (δ ppm) exhibited³

signals for C-10, C-11, C-6, C-9, C-7, C-8, C-1 and C-5 in the regions δ 132.18—133.85, 130.24—131.9, 136.28—137.98 and 66.94—69.23 (²J_{POC-1,C-5}, 0—7.0 Hz). The two methyl carbons resonated as a singlet at 19.17—19.29. The ¹³C nmr shifts of phenoxy moiety resonated in the expected range, and the signals for piperazine moiety appeared at δ 45.75 and 44.15 for C-2, C-6 and C-3, C-5. *p*-Chlorothiophenol moiety exhibited signals for C-1, C-2, C-6, and C-7, C-5 at δ 132.13, 131.34—128.93. The signal for C-4 was observed at δ 135.04.

The compounds (1d, g, h, l, m and 2a—e) were screened *in vitro* for anticholinesterase activity by the colorimetric technique⁴, using sheep liver as the source for the enzyme, α-naphthyl acetate as substrate and Fast Blue B (a diazonium salt) as the colouring agent. The results obtained were compared with the inhibitory effect at concentrations 5, 10 and 20 ppm of standard commercial pesticide-methyl parathion (Technical grade).

Experimental

All the melting points were determined on a Mel-temp apparatus and are uncorrected. Their spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian HA 100 spectrometer (100 MHz), ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a NT 360 WB spectrometer (90.50 MHz) with tetramethylsilane as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Krates MS-80 spectrometer (70 eV) at a resolution of 10000. The elemental analyses were performed at Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

4,5-Dimethyl-1,2-benzenedimethanol and phenylphosphorodichloridates were prepared as described in literature.

3-Phenoxy-1,5-dihydro-7,8-dimethyl-2,4,3-benzodioxaphosphepin-3-oxide (1b): Phenylphosphorodichloridate (1.05 g, 0.005 mol) in dry benzene (20 ml) was added to a stirred mixture of 4,5-dimethyl-1,2-benzenedimethanol (0.83 g, 0.005 mol) and triethylamine (1.01 g, 0.01 mol) in tetrahydrofuran (20 ml). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h and for another 2 h at 50—60°. The progress of

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NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (1a—m, 2a—e)*				
Compd.* no.	M.p. °C	¹ Hnmr δ, J(Hz)	¹³ C nmr δ, J(Hz)	m/z (%)
1a	120—21	2.33 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.02 (Ha), 5.30 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.3, J _p (Ha), 9.3, J _p (Hb) 10.2, 7.0—7.36 (7H, m, arom)	—	—
b	146—47	2.27 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.03 (Ha), 5.29 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.2, J _p (Ha) 10.1, J _p (Hb) 11.0, 7.07—7.35 (7H, m, arom)	—	—
c	83—90	2.25 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.03 (Ha), 5.30 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.1, J _p (Ha) 10.2, J _p (Hb) 12.5, 7.0—7.36 (6H, m, arom)	—	—
d	126—27	2.26 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.10(Ha), 5.26 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.2, J _p (Ha) 10.1, J _p (Hb) 12.6, 7.0—7.36 (6H, m, arom)	—	—
e	110—12	2.34 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.18 (Ha), 5.28 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.4, J _p (Ha) 9.2, J _p (Hb) 10.5, 7.0—7.37 (6H, m, arom)	—	318(22), 302(10), 220(8), 205(7), 181(15), 132(100), 117(12), 91(13), 77(8)
f	141—43	2.27 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.10 (Ha), 5.32 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.3, J _p (Ha) 10.2, J _p (Hb) 10.3, 7.07—7.34 (6H, m, arom)	68.83 (d, J 7.0), 130.44, 137.71, 132.39, 19.22, 150.20 (d, J 5.6), 120.20 (d, J 5.1), 140.1, 125.84, 129.41, 116.9, 21.21	318(12), 303(22), 288(36), 211(15), 181(100), 132(47), 91(5)
g	145—47	2.27 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.10 (Ha), 5.26 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.2, J _p (Ha) 10.0, J _p (Hb) 11.6, 7.18—7.26 (6H, m, arom), 2.33 (3H, s, CH ₃)	—	318(14), 303(22), 288(27), 181(91), 132(100), 91(54), 77(26)
h	134—35	2.27 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.07 (Ha), 5.30 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.0, J _p (Ha) 10.3, J _p (Hb) 12.4, 7.06—7.25 (6H, m, arom), 2.32 (3H, s), 1.98 (3H, s, CH ₃)	—	432(100), 317(31), 234(34), 132(100), 181(50), 117(17), 91(15)
	175—76	2.25 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.02 (Ha), 5.25 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.0, J _p (Ha) 10.0, J _p (Hb) 12.5, 7.0—7.32 (5H, m, arom), 2.35 (6H, s, CH ₃)	—	—
	148—50	2.24 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.04 (Ha), 5.35 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.3, J _p (Ha) 9.8, J _p (Hb) 12.8, 7.03—7.35 (5H, m, arom), 2.30 (6H, s, CH ₃)	68.79 (d, J 7.0), 130.42, 137.67, 132.42, 19.20, 148.20 (d, J 6.6), 120.55 (d, J 5.0), 138.26, 133.34, 130.5, 116.9 (d, J 4.5), 19.7, 18.92	—
k	119—20	2.26 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.16(Ha), 5.23 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.4, J _p (Ha) 9.5, J _p (Hb) 12.9, 6.81—7.25 (5H, m, arom), 2.29 (6H, s, CH ₃)	68.62 (d, J 6.8), 130.24, 137.47, 132.24, 19.17, 149.92 (d, J 6.22), 116.96 (d, J 3.7), 139.42, 126.54, 139.42, 116.96 (d, J 3.75), 20.91, 29.91	—
l	163—64	2.27 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.11 (Ha), 5.29 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.2, J _p (Ha) 9.6, J _p (Hb) 12.7, 7.03—7.71 (5H, m, arom), 2.35 (3H, s, CH ₃)	68.96 (d, J 7.0), 130.50, 37.88, 132.27, 19.27, 148.60, 122.04 (d, J 4.72), 137.81, 130.59, 129.96, 118.37 (d, J 4.9), 20.13	—
m	179—80	2.25 (s, 2CH ₃), 5.0 (Ha), 6.13 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.3, J _p (Ha) 11.2, J _p (Hb) 10.9, 7.0—7.54 (5H, m, arom)	69.23 (d, J 6.75), 130.62, 137.98, 132.18, 19.17, 145.01, 125.39, 128.08, 130.43, 130.05, 121.05	372(27), 230(9), 257(9), 181(100), 130(66), 132(44), 147(25), 91(25)
2a	249—50	4.7—5.50 (4H, m, 2CH ₂), 2.27 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 7.18 (2H, s), 3.1 (8H, s, 4CH ₂)	44.14, 130.65, 137.39, 133.85, 19.24	296(15), 217(50), 132(93), 86(100), 58(27)
b	229—30	—	—	—
c	144—45	5.08—5.45 (4H, m, 2CH ₂), 2.29 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 7.0—8.0 (8H, m, arom)	—	246(27), 147(67), 130(100), 119(42), 91(34)
d	124—25	4.1 (4H, s, 2CH ₂), 2.20 (s, 2CH ₃), 6.9 (2H, s), 7.18 (4H, s)	36.56, 131.88, 136.28, 132.49, 19.22, 132.13, 131.34, 128.93, 135.04	275(100), 163(53), 121(96), 117(64), 91(30)
e	94—95	4.75—5.60 (4H, m, 2CH ₂), 2.21 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 6.9—7.22 (7H, m), 2.35 (3H, s, N-CH ₃)	—	—

* All compounds gave satisfactory IR absorptions and elemental analyses.

† High resolution MS of 1h: 332.1166(18) C₁₈H₂₁O₄P, 317.0962(4.6) C₁₇H₁₈O₄P, 234.0962(5.9) C₁₈H₁₈, 219.1194 (4.3) C₁₇H₁₅, 147.0414(3.2) C₁₀H₁₁O, 130.0999 (15.3) C₁₀H₁₃, 132.0945(100) C₁₀H₁₂, 117.6723(11.8) C₉H₉, 91.0560

the reaction was monitored by tlc. Triethylamine-hydrochloride was separated by filtration, the solvent removed, the residue washed with water and recrystallised from benzene-hexane mixture (2 : 1) (860 mg, 57%), m.p 146–47°. Similarly other compounds (yield 53–63%) were prepared.

3-(1-Piperazinyl)-1,5-dihydro-7,8-dimethyl-2, 4, 3-benzodioxaphosphin-3-oxide (2a): Phosphorusoxychloride (0.77 g, 0.005 mol) in dry benzene (15 ml) was added to a cooled (5–10°) and stirred mixture of 4,5-dimethyl-1,2-benzenedimethanol (0.83 g, 0.005 mol) and triethylamine (1.56 g, 0.015 mol) in benzene (40 ml) and tetrahydrofuran (10 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and later at 40–60° for an additional 2 h. Piperazine (0.47 g, 0.005 mol) in tetrahydrofuran (15 ml) was then added to the reaction mixture at 10–15° while stirring. It was slowly brought to room temperature and stirred for an additional 2 h. Solid triethylaminehydrochloride was separated by filtration and the solvent from the filtrate was removed. The resulting solid was washed with water and purified by trituration with warm methanol and tetrahydrofuran and crystallised from propan-2-ol as a colourless crystals (868 mg, 58%). Similarly other compounds (yield 52–59%) were prepared.

Biological activity: A careful scrutiny of the data of 1a–m reveals that 1d appears to show higher

enzyme inhibition than 1g, h, l, m. The presence of electron-withdrawing groups may be responsible for the higher esterase inhibition when compared to electron-releasing groups attached to the phenoxy moiety.

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